

Different approaches to the PP-attachment problem in Polish

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Abstract

A number of approaches, using different available resources, were applied to the PP-attachment problem in Polish. Some methods were reimplementations of supervised and partially supervised models for English described in literature, others were our modifications and extensions, mostly using a wordnet for Polish. The best accuracy achieved on the final testing dataset was 75.7%, which is not much below the accuracy of an expert's decisions obtained in a pilot study.

1 Introduction

The PP-attachment problem consists in identifying correct attachment sites for prepositional phrases occurring in natural language utterances. A high-accuracy method for solving this problem can be useful in parsing and parse disambiguation for the purposes of creating treebanks as well as in any NLP application which requires full syntactic analysis of text. The typical formulation of the problem's single instance is a quadruple $(v, n, p, n2)$, with verb v and noun n being two possible attachment sites for a phrase headed by preposition p ¹ with a dependent noun $n2$. This work describes experiments on applying different approaches, using different available resources, to the PP-attachment problem in Polish.

2 Related work

A considerable amount of work has been devoted to the problem of PP-attachment, especially in English. Extensive research in what could be called a "partially supervised" framework was started by Hindle and Rooth [10] and followed by, among

¹Polish has some prepositions which have the same surface form, but select for different grammatical cases and have different meanings. Therefore, throughout this text, unless explicitly stated otherwise, by *preposition* we will mean its surface form together with the case.

others, Resnik and Hearst [21], Resnik [20], Ratnaparkhi [17, 18] and Pantel and Lin [14]. Another line of research was devoted to supervised methods, including work by Brill and Resnik [5], Ratnaparkhi et al. [19], Collins and Brooks [7], Stetina and Nagao [23], Zavrel et al. [28] and McLauchlan [13]. Volk [24], Kawahara and Kurohashi [11], Bharathi et al. [4], Roh et al. [22] and Coppola et al. [8] proposed approaches combining supervised and partially supervised methods or data. Foth and Menzel [9], Agirre et al. [2], Roh et al. [22] and Anguiano and Candito [3] presented work on incorporating PP-attachment resolution into parsing or parse correction. The problem of phrase attachment for Polish has already been addressed by Acedański et al. [1]. It is however difficult to directly compare their results with ours since their task is different and not restricted to PP-attachment.

3 Data sources

3.1 Fully annotated data: dependency treebanks

Currently, the largest manually constructed treebank for Polish is Krzaki² (*Bushes*), a collection of 20 000 unlabelled dependency structures for sentences picked randomly from the manually tagged subcorpus of National Corpus of Polish³ (NKJP, Przepiórkowski et al. [16]). 5734 lemmatised $(v, n, p, n2, a)$ quintuples, where a stands for either V (verb) or N (noun) attachment, were extracted from Krzaki. Each quintuple represents a dependency substructure where a verb v has an NP dependent (headed by n) or a PP dependent (with the head preposition’s dependent n), and a PP headed by p (with a dependent noun $n2$) is governed by either v or n (so that a is known), but both are syntactically possible as the PP’s attachment sites. Figure 1 shows schematically the types of dependency substructures from which the tuples were extracted.

The data was split into 3 groups: 50% training, 25% development and 25% set aside for final testing. Two split methods were used. In the first one, each tuple was assigned to a group separately, so tuples coming from one sentence could end up in different groups. Since the supervised methods explored in this work rely on lexical similarities between training data and new instances to be classified, this could cause an “information leak”.⁴ In the second split method, all quintuples generated from one sentence were required to end up in one group. The data sets obtained using these two strategies will be henceforth referred to as BY-TUPLE and BY-SENTENCE. The numbers of tuples in each dataset are given in Table 1.

A large, automatically obtained dependency treebank for Polish was created by Wróblewska and Przepiórkowski [26]. It consists of about 3 million trees for

²<http://zil.ipipan.waw.pl/Krzaki>

³<http://nkjp.pl>

⁴For example, if a sentence contains a sequence $V\ NP\ [p_1\ n_1]_{PP_1}\ [p_2\ n_2]_{PP_2}$ with the NP (headed by n) and the two PP’s being dependents of V , it generates, among others, two very similar quintuples (v, n, p_2, n_2, V) and (v, n_1, p_2, n_2, V) .

Figure 1: Dependency substructures and corresponding extracted quintuples.

	KRZAKI-TRAIN	KRZAKI-DEV	KRZAKI-TEST
BY-TUPLE	2867 (50%)	1434 (25%)	1433 (25%)
BY-SENTENCE	2810 (49%)	1504 (26%)	1420 (25%)

Table 1: Size of KRZAKI datasets (BY-TUPLE and BY-SENTENCE data splits).

sentences from a parallel, Polish-English corpus. The structure for each Polish sentence was projected from a dependency parse for its English counterpart. It is our belief that automatically obtained linguistic resources should be treated as less reliable than manually annotated ones, but the large size of the projected dependency treebank seems to have the potential to compensate for its possible overall correctness shortcomings. The same extraction procedure was applied to the treebank, yielding a set of 382 580 quintuples that will be referred to as PROJECTED.

3.2 Partially annotated data: NKJP

Some information useful for resolving the PP attachment problem can also be found in data that is not syntactically annotated. To explore this possibility, lemmatised triples of the form $(v, p, n2)$ and $(n, p, n2)$ were obtained from NKJP (restricted to book and press texts) using two heuristic queries. The V attachment query found snippets consisting of a VP followed by a PP.⁵ The N attachment query found fragments consisting of an NP followed by a PP, with the additional requirement that the two are preceded by a punctuation mark and an optional conjunction

⁵In Polish, such VP is not guaranteed to be the actual attachment site of the PP, but probably is.

or complement.⁶ One variant of the queries is given in Appendix A. Approximately 18 000 000 verb and 3 000 000 noun attachment examples were found. This data can be seen as training material in a partially supervised framework: examples of probable verb or noun attachments of PPs are available, but there are no examples of correct choice between two particular attachments, like in the previous dataset. Let us define here some counts obtained from this data that will be used in the paper (* means any word):

- $c(x, p)$: triples $(x, p, *)$, i.e., triples where p is governed by the word x ,
- $c(x)$: triples $(x, *, *)$, i.e., triples where some preposition is governed by x ,
- $c(V, p)$: triples $(v, p, *)$ where v is a verb,
- $c(N, p)$: triples $(n, p, *)$ where n is a noun,
- $c(V)$: triples $(v, *, *)$ where v is a verb (all examples of verb attachment),
- $c(N)$: triples $(n, *, *)$ where n is a noun (all examples of noun attachment).

A similar data extraction procedure can be found, e.g., in Kawahara and Kurohashi [11], who used a large raw corpus crawled from the web.

4 Experiments

4.1 Baselines

As a baseline, three simplistic models were tested:

Always verb. Always assign a verb attachment.

Partially supervised. Using the NKJP data, estimate the probability of a verb or noun being a governor of a given preposition p by $\frac{c(V,p)}{c(V)}$ and $\frac{c(N,p)}{c(N)}$ respectively; choose verb assignment iff the former is \geq than the latter.

Supervised. This is the “Most likely for each preposition” baseline proposed by Collins and Brooks [7]: choose the most frequent attachment seen for p in training data (KRZAKI-TRAIN from the respective split).

Accuracies achieved by the baselines are presented in Table 2. The results show that naïve models perform poorly: the overall accuracy is not much above 50%, although visibly better for the supervised baseline. The partially supervised baseline performs slightly worse than the “always verb” heuristic, although both are useless as PP-attachment models for Polish. For some comparison with baselines for the same problem in English, Hindle and Rooth [10] report an accuracy of 67% achieved by always choosing noun attachment on a manually constructed dataset. Collins and Brooks [7] provide two baseline results for another dataset. They report two strategies: “Always noun attachment”⁷ and “Most likely for each preposition” (as described above) to achieve accuracies of 59.0% and 72.2% respectively. The results for Polish are considerably lower, which is quite possibly

⁶The punctuation mark was introduced to heuristically reduce the snippets where some preceding phrase is the actual attachment site.

⁷Note that both cited English datasets are biased differently than our: towards noun attachment.

due to the problem being more difficult, but one has to bear in mind that this is a comparison across different languages and datasets (the impact of datasets variability on comparability of results for PP-attachment is discussed by Volk [25]).

	BY-TUPLE	BY-SENTENCE
Always verb	55.4%	57.0%
Partially supervised	54.9%	56.3%
Supervised	61.7%	63.4%

Table 2: Baseline accuracy on KRZAKI-DEV.

4.2 Partially supervised approach

Given a quadruple $(v, n, p, n2)$, the information from triples extracted from NKJP was used to determine the PP’s attachment site. Following the estimation proposed by Hindle and Rooth [10] and also used by Ratnaparkhi [18], the probabilities of verb and noun attachment were calculated respectively as $P(p|v) = \frac{c(v,p) + \frac{c(v,p)}{c(v)}}{c(v)+1}$ and $P(p|n) = \frac{c(n,p) + \frac{c(n,p)}{c(n)}}{c(n)+1}$. Verb attachment was chosen if $\log P(p|v) - \log P(p|n)$ was above or equal certain threshold (experimentally set to -0.1). A minimal required number of occurrences of $(v, p, *)$ and $(n, p, *)$ triples was experimentally set to 50. If an attachment site n or v occurred with p less than 50 times, the corresponding triples were discarded from training data.

In a second experiment, each preposition p was replaced with a pair (p, c) where c is the semantic category of $n2$ from PLWORDNET⁸ (Piasecki et al. [15]). Semantic categories, such as *place*, *animal* or *event*, are a coarse-grained classification of PLWORDNET’s lexical units (i.e., words with particular meanings assigned). A uniform distribution of meanings was assumed in case of ambiguous words: each triple $(x, p, n2)$ was treated as k triples with a $\frac{1}{k}$ weight (where k is the number of possible meanings of $n2$), one for each meaning’s category. When a quadruple $(v, n, p, n2)$ was to be classified, attachment was chosen for each of $n2$ ’s possible meanings separately, and the more frequent decision was taken as the final attachment.

Accuracies of both methods are presented in Table 3. The first experiment shows a substantial improvement over the supervised baseline presented before: the accuracies on both DEV datasets were raised by over 10 percentage points, reducing the error by 30.3% and 27.6% respectively. Incorporating semantic categories into the model brings about further, although less spectacular, improvement: 3.6 and 2.0 percentage points respectively (13.5% and 7.5% error reduction). These figures show that lexical information (even obtained in a heuristic way) is crucial for solving the PP attachment. For comparison, Hindle and Rooth [10] report an

⁸<http://plwordnet.pwr.wroc.pl/wordnet>

accuracy of about 80% for English achieved by a very similar method (without semantic categories) on their data.

	BY-TUPLE	BY-SENTENCE
Preposition	73.3%	73.5%
Preposition+category	76.9%	75.5%

Table 3: Partially supervised method’s accuracy on KRZAKI-DEV.

4.3 Supervised approach: backed-off model

In an experiment with a supervised approach, the backed-off model (Collins and Brooks [7]) was used. This method of PP attachment disambiguation relies on examples from the training data which are similar to the instance to be classified. Given a quadruple $(v, n, p, n2)$ for which the PP attachment should be chosen, the procedure is as follows:

- Check whether any quintuples of the form $(v, n, p, n2, a)$ appeared in the training data. If so, the attachment is chosen to be the more frequent one among those training quintuples (V in case of a tie).
- If no matching data was found, search for quintuples matching on only 3 among v, n, p and $n2$, but require matching p . Therefore, all quintuples of the form $(v', n, p, n2, a)$, $(v, n', p, n2, a)$ and $(v, n, p, n2', a)$ are taken into account. As above, the more frequent attachment is chosen.
- If no matching data was found, back-off to quintuples matching on 2 coordinates including p : $(v', n', p, n2, a)$, $(v', n, p, n2', a)$ and $(v, n', p, n2', a)$.
- If no matching data was found, back-off to quintuples matching only on p .
- If all the above failed, choose V attachment as default.

Together with the decision about attachment, the level at which it was taken is returned (4 if all four v, n, p and $n2$ could be taken into account at once; 3 if it was backed-off to matching only three; ...; 0 if the default V attachment was chosen). Results obtained in experiments with different testing/training data setups are listed in Table 4.

The model’s accuracy generally deteriorates with the back-off level, which is intuitive and in compliance with the results reported by Collins and Brooks [7]. In both cases, the results for levels 4 and 3 are similar and relatively high. Unfortunately, the quadruples classified at those levels constitute 20% and 8% of the respective test data. The coverage does not approach 100% until level 1. In the case of the model trained on the PROJECTED dataset, the testing data coverage on levels 4 and 3 is higher (36%/38% for BY-TUPLE/BY-SENTENCE). Moreover, coverage exceeds 95% already at level 2. Nevertheless, the performance is worse, which leads to a lower total accuracy. These results show that, despite being much smaller, the manually annotated data provide a more reliable source of training

train	test	4	3	2	1	0	total
KRZAKI-TRAIN BY-TUPLE	KRZAKI-DEV BY-TUPLE	94.7%	95.4%	72.8%	59.7%	50.0%	73.2%
instances classified		19	260	717	434	4	
coverage		1.3%	19.5%	69.5%	99.7%	100%	
KRZAKI-TRAIN BY-SENTENCE	KRZAKI-DEV BY-SENTENCE	86.7%	83.5%	72.2%	66.3%	76.2%	71.3%
instances classified		15	103	893	472	21	
coverage		1.0%	7.8%	67.2%	98.6%	100%	
PROJECTED	KRZAKI-DEV BY-TUPLE	82.5%	66.4%	65.3%	63.2%	100.0%	66.3%
instances classified		57	458	880	38	1	
coverage		4.0%	35.9%	97.3%	99.9%	100%	
PROJECTED	KRZAKI-DEV BY-SENTENCE	72.4%	70.9%	66.4%	61.5%	100.0%	68.0%
instances classified		58	506	887	52	1	
coverage		3.9%	37.5%	96.5%	99.9%	100%	

Table 4: Accuracy of the backed-off model tested on KRZAKI-DEV datasets. Besides total results, accuracies achieved at each back-off level are given. The numbers of classified quadruples as well as coverage at each level are also given. A level’s coverage is the percentage of quadruples classified at this or higher levels.

examples. It also suggests that the backed-off model can be rather sensitive to more noise in training data. What is more, the model yields worse results than the partially supervised method. For comparison, Collins and Brooks [7] report an accuracy of 84.1% for English.

In the case of models trained on KRZAKI-TRAIN datasets, a quite large discrepancy is visible between results for BY-TUPLE and BY-SENTENCE splits, both in coverage and performance on different levels. In the case of BY-TUPLE datasets, the accuracies are generally higher. The increase of coverage on level 3 is also more visible. This is possibly due to the BY-TUPLE split making it easier for the backed-off model to achieve better results (as discussed above), which was a motivation for testing different data split strategies in the first place. Assuming that the adopted split strategy influences the results, it should be expected that with other training data, unrelated to KRZAKI and independent of the particular split, this tendency would disappear. As a matter of fact, when the respective KRZAKI-TRAIN dataset is replaced with PROJECTED as training data (see the lower part of Table 4), the results for particular levels are no longer so different between BY-TUPLE and BY-SENTENCE datasets. Following those observations, the results of further experiments will be given only for BY-SENTENCE split.

4.4 Lexical generalisations of the backed-off model

Since the backed-off model performs at its best for quadruples for which there are very similar examples in the training data, it seems worthwhile to try increasing its coverage at higher levels without much accuracy loss. One can therefore think of generalising the information contained in training data in order to find matches for more classified instances. One idea is to relax the requirement for matching tuples by taking into account synonymy relations between words.

It seems that the verb lemma is a kind of information which is very specific and should not be lost. This is because verbs tend to have strong selective preferences on prepositional phrases and even ones very close in meaning may differ in that respect, especially when the PP can fill an argument position. However, it is our intuition that replacing a noun with its synonym can help find better evidence in training data. A modification to the backed-off model as described above was therefore introduced. For a quadruple (v, n, p, n_2) , all the combinations (v, n', p, n_2') were generated where n' and n_2' share a PLWORDNET synset with any meaning of n and n_2 respectively. Classification was performed for each “synonymous” tuple separately. The final decision was the most frequent one on the highest possible level (V in case of a tie). The results obtained for this procedure are listed in Table 5. A slight increase in coverage at levels 3 and 4 is visible, but no significant improvement was observed. The overall accuracy is lower than that of the “standard” backed-off model (71.3%).

train	test	4	3	2	1	0	total
KRZAKI-TRAIN BY-SENTENCE	KRZAKI-DEV BY-SENTENCE	87.5%	80.7%	71.3%	65.9%	76.2%	70.8%
instances classified		16	119	931	417	21	
coverage		1.1%	9.0%	70.9%	98.6%	100%	

Table 5: Accuracy of the backed-off model augmented with synonyms.

Another experiment was performed using lists of distributional semantic similarity⁹ created at Wrocław University of Technology using the SuperMatrix tool (Broda and Piasecki [6]). For each word accounted for, a list of 20 most similar words extracted from a large collection of texts is provided. The words in the lists are not sense-disambiguated. The experiment with similarity lists was analogous to the synset-based one, except that the synonyms retrieved from synsets were replaced with contents of similarity lists. The results are listed in Table 6. The accuracy results are better than the previous ones, an improvement in terms of tuple coverage is also visible.

The synset-based approach described above only took into account synonymy understood as being in the same synset: two words are either considered synonymous or completely unrelated. It seems that such approach has two major limita-

⁹<http://nlp.pwr.wroc.pl/en/tools-and-resources/msr-list>

train	test	4	3	2	1	0	total
KRZAKI-TRAIN BY-SENTENCE	KRZAKI-DEV BY-SENTENCE	78.9%	80.7%	70.9%	68.1%	76.2%	72.3%
instances classified		19	259	995	210	21	
coverage		1.3%	18.5%	84.6%	98.6%	100.0%	

Table 6: Accuracy of the backed-off model augmented with similar words.

tions. First, PLWORDNET’s synsets tend to be small: in version 2.2 used in the experiment described in this section, the average number of lexical units per synset is 1.37 (76% of synsets containing one lexical unit) for nouns and 1.49 (73% of synsets containing one lexical unit) for verbs. Therefore, each word has very few (if any) synonyms. Second, a much better use could be made of the wordnet’s structure by calculating a wordnet-based word similarity measures and therefore “quantifying” the similarity between words.

In the next experiment, we use the following formula given by Wu and Palmer [27] for measuring similarity between two concepts (synsets) c_1 and c_2 :

$$dist(c_1, c_2) = \frac{2 \cdot depth(C)}{d(c_1, C) + d(c_2, C) + 2 \cdot depth(C)}$$

where C is the lowest common hypernym of c_1 and c_2 ; $depth(c)$ is the depth of concept c , i.e., length of the path connecting it to a root concept; and $d(c, c')$ is the length of the path connecting concepts c and c' . The distance between c_1 and c_2 can be calculated using the above formula as $1 - dist(c_1, c_2)$. Note that the resulting value will always be between 0 and 1. Following the approach adopted in many works concerning wordnet-based similarity/distance measures, the distance between two words is the minimum distance between their possible meanings.

Some transformations (most notably extending the hypernymy relation using some other relations) were performed on PLWORDNET to better suit it to computing Wu-Palmer distance; due to space limitations, we omit the details of those transformations. The original backed-off model was then modified by redefining the notion of matching tuples. Instead of requiring lemmata of words forming two tuples to be identical, the tuples are considered matching if the Wu-Palmer distances between words at respective positions do not exceed a given threshold. Two variants of this method were tested. In the first one, the distance between two words was calculated as in the formula above – by finding the minimum over all their meanings. In the second one, Plukb, a WSD tool created at Wrocław University of Technology (Kędzia et al. [12]), was used to restrict the senses to a single one where possible. The tool is still under development, but the experiment was nevertheless performed to see how the use of WSD would affect the results. Table 7 presents results obtained using different thresholds, with and without WSD. The highest accuracy of 72.5%, was achieved using a 0.05 threshold with WSD. It is very slightly better than the similarity lists approach, and still below the accuracy of the partially supervised method. The failure to outperform it may be due to

the massive amounts of data collected from NKJP outweighing the benefit from syntactically annotated data and supervised learning.

variant	4	3	2	1	0	total
thr=0.05	85.0%	78.6%	72.5%	65.8%	76.2%	71.9%
instances classified at each level coverage	20 1.3%	145 11.0%	1002 77.6%	316 98.6%	21 100.0%	
thr=0.1	85.7%	76.7%	71.8%	67.7%	76.2%	72.1%
instances classified at each level coverage	21 1.4%	202 14.8%	1034 83.6%	226 98.6%	21 100.0%	
thr=0.2	78.0%	71.6%	72.4%	66.2%	76.2%	72.0%
instances classified at each level coverage	50 3.3%	563 40.8%	793 93.5%	77 98.6%	21 100.0%	
thr=0.05, +WSD	84.2%	80.5%	73.0%	67.5%	76.2%	72.5%
instances classified at each level coverage	19 1.3%	133 10.1%	980 75.3%	351 98.6%	21 100.0%	
thr=0.1, +WSD	84.2%	79.5%	72.0%	66.9%	76.2%	72.0%
instances classified at each level coverage	19 1.3%	151 11.3%	1038 80.3%	275 98.6%	21 100.0%	
thr=0.2, +WSD	85.2%	74.3%	71.3%	64.9%	76.2%	71.7%
instances classified at each level coverage	27 1.8%	327 23.5%	995 89.7%	134 98.6%	21 100.0%	

Table 7: Accuracy of different variants of the the backed-off model with wordnet distance on KRZAKI-DEV (BY-SENTENCE split).

McLauchlan [13] also experimented with extending the backed-off method: by smoothing the backed-off estimates using different thesauruses for English, he improved the accuracy from 84.3% to 85.1%.

4.5 Results on final testing data

The experiments described above allowed to establish the variants of the partially supervised and supervised (backed-off) methods performing best of the KRZAKI-DEV dataset from BY-SENTENCE split. Among the two tested partially supervised models, the one with PLWORDNET semantic categories turned out to achieve the higher accuracy of 75.5%. The best-performing backed-off variant was the wordnet-distance based one with WSD, with a result of 72.5% for its best settings. In order to complete the experiments, the two models were tested on KRZAKI-TEST dataset from BY-SENTENCE split. The partially supervised model with semantic categories and the supervised model achieved accuracies of 75.7% and 69.6% respectively (see Table 8 for detailed results of the backed-off model). The results confirm the superiority of the partially supervised model. They also show a certain stability of its performance when tested on KRZAKI-DEV and KRZAKI-TEST. The backed-off model performs surprisingly poorly, which is even more disappointing

given that, unlike the NKJP-trained, partially supervised one, it was trained on data originating from the same resource. It would be much more interesting to compare the models’ accuracies across testing datasets extracted from different sources, but we currently have no possibility to obtain reliable data of this kind.

variant	4	3	2	1	0	total
thr=0.05, +WSD	100.0%	85.8%	69.3%	64.7%	38.5%	
instances classified at each level	8	134	911	354	13	69.6%
coverage	0.6%	10.0%	74.2%	99.1%	100.0%	

Table 8: Accuracy of the selected backed-off model variant on KRZAKI-TEST (BY-SENTENCE split).

4.6 Comparison with human performance

To provide a kind of upper bound for assessing the tested methods’ performance, a linguist manually disambiguated 200 cases taken from Krzaki in a pilot study. The human annotator was given only the information available to the models: two possible governors and the PP truncated to the preposition and noun. Agreement between the attachments chosen by the annotator and extracted from Krzaki was 79% (83% if discarding 10 cases deemed too ambiguous by the linguist). The measures should be treated as a very rough approximation given the small size of data, but they suggest that the described task is difficult. On the positive side, the presented methods are not very far below this human performance. Perhaps a hybrid method, combining multiple models, data and features, could achieve results comparable to a human annotator when given a limited context.

5 Conclusions and further work

Various methods of solving the PP-attachment problem were tested for Polish. Some of them were reimplementations of techniques described in literature, some were our own extensions and ideas. The obtained results are quite good, but still below the “human” upper bound. The amount of work devoted to this problem for English shows that there is much room for further exploration. The models tested in this work mostly rely on the limited context of the $(v, n, p, n2)$ quadruple (only the senses from the WSD tool were obtained using whole corresponding sentences) and all achieve similar results. It seems that at least two general areas are worth investigation. One is using a wider context for PP disambiguation, the other is moving from the “isolated” $(v, n, p, n2)$ case to efficient PP attachment disambiguation in full sentence parsing.

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A NKJP queries

- verb attachment:

```
[pos="qub" & base="się"]? [pos="adv"]{,2}
[pos="fin|praet|impt|imps|inf|pcon|pact|ger"]
[pos="qub" & base="by"]? [pos="aglt"]?
[pos="qub" & base="się"]? [pos="adv"]{,2}
[pos="prep" & case~$1] [pos="adv"]{,2}
[pos="adj" & case~$1]* [pos="subst" & case~$1]
meta channel="prasa|ksiazka"
```

- noun attachment:

```
[pos="interp"] [pos="conj|comp"]?
[pos="adv"]{,2} [pos="adj" & case~$2]* [pos="subst" & case~$2]
[pos="prep" & case~$1] [pos="adv"]{,2}
[pos="adj" & case~$1]* [pos="subst" & case~$1]
meta channel="prasa|ksiazka"
```